

ENTANGLING FAMILY DYNAMICS AND TRANSGENERATIONAL TRAUMA: A STUDY OF SHAMSIE'S *SALT AND SAFFRON*

Sidra Bukhari

tehseens277@gmail.com

Government Graduate College, Gojra Road, Jhang (Pakistan).

Muhammad Tayyib Aijaz

tayyibijaz@gmail.com

Assistant Professor in English, Government Graduate College,
Gojra Road, Jhang

Sara Anam

saraxp29@gmail.com

Lecturer, Riphah International University, Faisalabad, Punjab,
Pakistan.

Abstract

Class differences create divisions and influence relationships. The India and Pakistan partition serves as a backdrop, with its legacy of separation and resentment in the family's internal conflicts, and the larger socio-cultural context. The *Salt and Saffron* explores identity, class, family relationships, and love that have a great impact on the Indian-Pakistan partition. The aims and objectives of this research are to explore how the novel depicts entangling family dynamics. It further explores how the trauma of partition travels in generations. It explores the reasons behind chaos in a post-independence world. Furthermore, this chapter explores a qualitative approach for research, and the primary source for this study is *Salt and Saffron*, and the secondary source includes all articles, quotes, and papers to support this research. There is no need for a qualitative approach because the data is not present in numerical form. This is a powerful postcolonial narrative that explores the lasting effects of colonization and the complex nature of identity in a post-independence world. The story also contrasts traditional societal expectations, particularly concerning Women and social Class, with the more modern point of view of characters exploring themes of empowerment and evolving gender roles. This research challenges the patriarchal norms and power dynamics that tried to oppress and marginalize women with resilience and strong determination.

Keywords: *Authoritative Structure, Cultural Imperialism, Discrimination, Equality, Feminist, Gender Rights, Oppression, Patriarchy, Resilience, Resistance.*

Corresponding Author: Sidra Bukhari (Government Graduate College, Gojra Road, Jhang (Pakistan).)

Email: tehseens277@gmail.com

1. Introduction

Salt and Saffron (2000) is a great novel presented by Pakistani author Kamila Shamsie that explores identity, Class, power dynamics, family, and the lasting impact of the India-Pakistan Partition. The story follows a Young Women who return to her aristocratic Pakistani family living in the US and UK. Through compelling family legends and subtle societal differences, the novel examines the distorted nature of stories, the complexities of identity, and how past events continue to shape the present. The novel delves into the rich, often exaggerated stories that stem from a family history, revealing how they influence present-day perception and identity. The deep-rooted prejudice surrounding class and cast in the aristocratic Pakistani families influences relationships.

The historical events of the India-Pakistan partition serve as a backdrop with its legacy of separation and the family internal conflicts and larger social culture. This novel revolves around the royal family of Dard-e-dils. This is a powerful postcolonial narrative that explores the lasting effects of colonization and the complex nature of identity in a post-independence world. The story also contrasts traditional societal expectations, particularly concerning Women and social Class, with the more modern point of view of characters exploring themes of empowerment and evolving gender roles. The story depicts Pakistani culture and identity with complexities and diversity in a great manner.

1.1. Statement of the problem

In Shamsie's *Salt and Saffron*, the concept of 'Statement problem' can refer to the various social, cultural, and historical challenge that the characters faces, particularly concerning issues of class, gender, memory, and the partition of India and colonialism. The novel explores the socio-economic division within Pakistani society, which is presented through food and the interaction between the elite Dard-e-dil family and those of lower social status, such as the family's cook. The 'statement problem' of the past, including the trauma partition and the complex relationship between oral family history and the written national history, profoundly understanding their individual and collective identities. The novel uses the interconnected stories of three generations of Women from the aristocratic Dard-e-dils family to examine how these 'problems', such as defying traditional patriarchal structures, the complex relationship, and the struggle for cultural identity in a post-colonial world, are confronted and, at times, resolved through acts of love, resistance, and remembrance. 'Statement problem', social, etc. and issues faced by the characters and their society.

1.2. Research Objectives

The aims and objectives of this research are:

- To explore how the novel represents complex and entangling family dynamics and the ways interpersonal relationships shape the lives and identities of the characters.

- To investigate how the trauma of the Partition is transmitted across generations and how historical violence continues to influence the psychological and emotional lives of later generations.
- To analyze the socio-political and psychological factors that contribute to the sense of chaos, uncertainty, and fragmentation in the post-independence world depicted in the novel.

1.3. Research Questions

1. How does the novel portray complex and entangling family dynamics and their impact on the identities and relationships of the characters?
2. In what ways does the trauma of the Partition travel across generations and affect the lives of subsequent characters?
3. What socio-political and psychological factors contribute to the chaos and instability in the post-independence world represented in the novel?

1.4. Research Significance

Class differences create divisions in relationships. The India and Pakistan partition serves as a backdrop, with its legacy of separation and resentment in the family's internal conflicts, and the larger socio-cultural context. The *Salt and Saffron* explores identity, class, family relationships, and love that have a great impact on the Indian-Pakistan partition. The previous research examines the distorted nature of stories, the complexities of identity, and how past events continue to shape the present. I have explored the angle of transgenerational theory. This Transgenerational theory, developed in psychology and family studies, suggests that unresolved trauma, beliefs, behaviors, and emotional patterns are unconsciously passed down across generations. It has great significance and often applies to families who experienced war, migration, colonialism, or cultural upheaval. Colonial and partition trauma ripple across generations. It transmits both cultural pride and psychological wounds. Healing requires confronting silent histories rather than letting them unconsciously dictate the present. This research explores these angles help the future researchers more angles to the coming generation so that they look forward this novel in a different way.

2. Literature Review

Shirazi, (2014) states that the writers of English literature describe the irony and residing in the land distinct from their homelands. The need for global culture undermines the role of native trends in English literature, describing the absolute influence of global culture and the transgenerational impact of the past colonial nation on natives and their cultural values. They use linguistic media to reinforce their local tradition and cultures; they are successful in revitalizing their native language, but are simultaneously undermined by using the hegemonic and powerful cultural values. The models of power, knowledge, and techno-scientific control are equipped to revive their local linguistics and

models with connectedness to their land. The novel *Salt and Saffron* are effective in reconciling the forces of globalization and tradition and modernity about the past and present. The spirits are rendered pointless; the modern contacts are different from those of pre-partitionon India. The old generation implies that the generation is in an endless lamentation of past glory. The old generation still strongly holds *Salt and Saffron*, effectively constructing a new national culture of Pakistani society with diversity of colors and conflicting values. In a playful opt an,m static attempt to learn about the past and move on with time, a new beginning, they are referring to the universal particular by dramatizing situations from their native lands (Shirazi, 2014).

Riaz & Babae (2015) discuss that exposure is a great cause of the growing consciousness, the unwanted consciousness acceptance of the new, and what is present. The experience suffers from trait means the anxiety of their personality, their respective cultures of traditions, relationships, food, clothes, and language. The expatriates of the consciousness of its origin in Indian soil, and the awareness of the expatriates who question about identity and origin, a recent study investigates and displays International Women's Day in collaboration to support women in the major cities of Pakistan. The people they passed they study developed new ideas to discover an underlying social phenomenon. From their perspective on the study, feminism is a social phenomenon and cultural norms of contemporary Pakistani society. They explore the dynamics of social and cultural differences in the status of men and women in the political context of Pakistan; their social and economic constraints cause distrust in their lives, their identity, and they feel threatened and need a secure environment. This acceptance is without bewilderment for her secure moment of life is union with characters. They analyzed the story of a person with two aspects of personality they are feelings and emotions related to the origin of one's existence. Internationals is designed for a target group that has conceptualized the Western slogans of women's preoccupation with the body (Riaz & Babae , 2015).

Nazeer, Sharif, Ali & Ahmad (2022) state that narrator belongs to the same family and believes the art of storytelling runs in the family. The novel shows the reason behind the Muslim families after the partition of Pakistan and India, but this is not the main subject of the novel. The analysis of the novel's subject by exploring the selected language techniques one by one. This is a technique where some words are left without translation as the postcolonial text is written in another language. This use of this technique is observed in *Salt and Saffron*, where native speakers use new words to represent the new innovative ideas, concepts, and practices. A close textual analysis of *Salt and Saffron* that concludes Shamsie's use of most of the language out of those nine techniques. It is observed that like all Past writers has appropriated in her novel to emphasize on the origin plays and people discussed in the novel the analysis of the novel subject discussion by the selected language is a blend or a combined of two dissimilar linguistic structure the novel

is based on the story of a Muslim family uses many terms from religion these food items are realistic for their taste and the words (Nazeer, Sharif, Ali & Ahmad, 2022).

Khan, Uzair & Zeb (2020) explore how Shamsie has tried to portray the culture of a certain Nawab family through the skillful use of language. It is difficult to ignore culture being used in another part of culture, another part of the world. There is a mention of a wedding where people have been invited to the celebration. The novel is a reference to the tasty foods made by the dishes of *Salt and Saffron* in Pakistani culture. The reader of foreign culture finds it difficult to describe the meaning of a sentence, the background of the sentence, the strange man the joint family system respect their opinions in almost all matters of day to day life. The novel by Kamila Shamsi, a writer of Pakistani origin, is a good example of culture in language in this novel communicates cultural aspects of a society in which the novel has been set. The mention of a Rajput Prince is about her beauty, who was abducted by one of her guards on the battlefield, to prevent the enemy soldiers from seeing their swords and start writing gazelle is a historical reference to the Dard-e-Dil family, the use of that unique term in Path Pakistan-ion text (Khan, Uzair & Zeb, 2020).

Sana & Muhammad (2021) explore that *The Holy Woman* (2001) by Qaisra Sheraz has the repetition of Urdu words. It described design data reasons for accumulating data models of linguistic features of South Asian English and data analysis, the ideology is related to fraud in Pakistan through language use in the novel. Many Pakistani novels depict the society, culture, and traditional norms. These two factors are most common in code-mixed words in the social culture or cultural context. It has different conceptual aspects of the two main factors, which mainly affirm the socio-cultural identity of the writers. The novel says reality different categories mentioned are social gathering, lexical, and marriage, which defeat the social and cultural norms. The research has been conducted in every single language, and no language is subordinate. Their works on Pakistani English novels, apart from the novel, can be organized through written discourse and through short stories. These can be Pakistani spoken different television and about the motto, the names of places, and so on, display a complete picture of society. The novel morphological innovation of native words in a feature of Pakistani English in this novel is the main word change of the English grammatical patterns (Sana & Muhammad, 2021).

Shoaib's (2019) study has a close relationship to issues like cultural identity, history, gender relations, and intelligence. The novelist constructs the notion of cultural superiority, gender biases, and class consciousness. It further explores the subversive in which food imagery, mythologies, and personal disrupt deconstruct the grand narrative in the Indo-Pak history. The intersection between the oral history of the Dard e Dil family of the Partition of India, the tension between the traditional fears and prejudices guarded and cherished by the new generation, and the viability of those prejudices. They explore dynamics of food politics in the Pakistani novel *Salt and Saffron*, how food is not merely

associated but charged with political and social meanings, the religious significance of food and through examination, the act of cooking and eating, the historical and religious discourse through culinary lands, the food is also used to marginalize, at the same time, counter such discourses. The appropriation of the space to subvert the servant binary has been highlighted. They discuss the literal and the representation of food culture, the species associated with it, and the use of food images. The meeting between Alia and Khalil points to the fair fact that food and places not only bring people together but also add them to religious devotion rather than culinary devotion (Shoaib, 2019).

3. Theoretical Framework

The concept of trauma has evolved beyond the boundaries of psychology to become one of the central frameworks in literary and cultural studies. Among the most influential figures in this field, Cathy Caruth (2014) has made a significant contribution by redefining trauma as an experience that is not merely psychological but also linguistic, historical, and trans-generational. Her theory explores how trauma exceeds the limits of ordinary understanding, disrupts language, and is transmitted across generations through memory, silence, and narrative. In her seminal work *Unclaimed Experience: Trauma, Narrative, and History* (1996), Caruth (2014) draws on psychoanalysis, deconstruction, and literary theory to explain how trauma is an “unclaimed experience,” an event so overwhelming that the individual cannot fully comprehend it when it occurs. This unprocessed experience returns repeatedly in the form of symptoms, dreams, and narratives. Caruth’s theory becomes particularly relevant in understanding trans-generational trauma, where the impact of historical or collective suffering (such as war, exile, or Partition) is passed on to subsequent generations who did not directly experience it.

Cathy Caruth defines trauma as a paradoxical experience, both a wound and a survival of the wound. It is an event that the mind cannot fully register when it happens. The shock and intensity of the experience cause a psychological disconnection between the event and its comprehension. For Caruth, trauma is experienced too soon, too unexpectedly, to be fully known and is therefore not available to consciousness until it imposes itself again, repeatedly. This delay or belatedness is central to her argument. Trauma is not the original event itself, but the way it returns in memory, dreams, or repetition. The victim relives the traumatic event as if it were happening again, unable to control or interpret it. Caruth extends this individual experience to the collective and cultural level, suggesting that trauma can affect communities, nations, and families often transmitted through storytelling, silence, or shared memory.

Caruth’s theory is deeply intertextual and inter-theoretical. She draws from psychoanalysis, post-structuralism, and memory studies, engaging with various thinkers. Each of these theorists contributes to her understanding of trauma as an experience that disrupts time, language, and identity. Freud’s psychoanalytic writings form the foundation

of Caruth's theory. In *Beyond the Pleasure Principle* (1920), Freud introduces the concept of repetition compulsion, where the victim unconsciously re-enacts traumatic events instead of remembering them. The psyche attempts to master the trauma by repeating it, but this repetition only deepens the wound. Caruth also draws on Jacques Lacan's notion of the Real, which represents the dimension of experience that cannot be captured by language. The Real is what resists symbolization, the unspeakable trauma that language fails to express. Lacan divides human experience into three orders: the Imaginary (images and identifications), the Symbolic (language and social order), and the Real (that which cannot be symbolized). Trauma belongs to the Real because it disrupts the coherence of the Symbolic world.

The trauma is not only about the event but also about the challenge of narrating it. In the process of testimony, the trauma is re-experienced, and both the speaker and the listener are transformed. Caruth extends this idea by emphasizing that trauma is transmitted not only through explicit testimony but also through what is left unsaid through silence, hesitations, and fragmented narratives. The listener becomes a secondary witness, inheriting part of the trauma. Dominick La Capra (1939) distinguishes between two responses to trauma: acting out and working through. Acting out means the individual is trapped in a cycle of repetition, reliving the trauma without understanding it. Working through involves confronting and narrating the trauma, integrating it into a larger understanding of history and identity. Caruth overlaps with LaCapra in viewing trauma as repetitive and unresolved. However, she focuses more on the linguistic and narrative dimension of the way trauma both resists and demands retelling. Marianne Hirsch's concept of post memory directly complements Caruth's trans-generational focus. Post memory refers to the relationship that later generations have to the trauma of their parents or ancestors. Even though they did not experience the events themselves, they inherit emotional memories through stories, photographs, and behaviors. In *Salt and Saffron*, Aliya's sense of displacement and confusion mirrors Hirsch's post-memory. She is haunted by events she never witnessed: the family's exile, divisions, and losses. Her emotional inheritance embodies Caruth's idea that trauma transcends time, carried through narrative silences and unconscious repetition.

Cathy Caruth's Trans generational Trauma Theory provides a profound lens for understanding how the past never truly disappears but echoes through generations, families, and nations. By integrating Freud's psychoanalysis, Lacan's linguistic theory, Felman and Laub's testimony model, LaCapra's historical approach, and Hirsch's post memory, Caruth constructs a multi-layered understanding of trauma as belated, unspeakable, and transmissible. Kamila Shamsie's *Salt and Saffron* vividly embodies these ideas. The Dard-e-Dil family's silences, myths, and emotional disconnection demonstrate how trauma can persist long after the original event. Through Aliya's

awakening, Shamsie portrays the possibility of reclaiming history through narrative, an act of “working through” that allows healing to begin. Ultimately, both Caruth’s theory and Shamsie’s fiction remind us that trauma is not only a wound of the past but a living presence, transmitted through words, silences, and memory waiting to be acknowledged so it can finally be understood.

4. Analysis and Discussion

Salt and Saffron explores how family history, identity, memory, and silence shape the lives of individuals in a well-known aristocratic family, which shaped her family's identity across generations. The study aims to examine how *Salt and Saffron* portray the entangled family dynamics of the Dard-e-dil family, where relationships are inherited by stories, silences, and the pressure of maintaining family prestige. The trauma of partition continues to affect generations, through direct memory but through emotional patterns, displacement, and identity. Family members' unspoken and unresolved history demonstrates the Transgenerational theory. The individuals struggle to redefine their identities in a formed nation. Transgenerational Theory shows that identity is not formed individually, but is inherited through family stories, silences, emotional wounds, and cultural memory. Aliya learns that to understand who she is, she must confront not only the beautiful stories (saffron), but also the painful truths (salt) hidden across generations.

First research question discussed about the family dynamics that are ‘entangled’ because past decisions continue to shape present relationships, and no family member is truly free of the family’s emotional history. “In Massachusetts, it was the memory of that titled head which kept me from writing to Dadi. I suppose the title encapsulated for me the way Dadi behaved about Mariam apa” (Shamsie, 2000, P. 5). The narrator's relationship with Dadi is shaped not by directed communication, but by memory and emotional inheritance. The symbolized silent judgment is an unspoken tension. The family bond is strong, yet strained, showing how past interactions continue to influence the present. This reflects generational emotional entanglement where feelings are remembered rather than expressed. The novel portrays the family dynamics as relationships, where personal desires conflict, and societal pressures and characters’ interactions. “Our love stories are all about pining and separation and tiny gestures assuming grand significance, but Celeste rolled her eyes. Hormones are hormones, she said. Khaleel. Khaleel. Khaleel” (Shamsie, 2000, p. 99). Love is shown through cultural storytelling vs. personal experience. The narrator romanticizes longing and emotional intensity, while Celeste dismisses it as biological. This contrast shows conflicting value systems within the family and their social circle. Even relationships outside the family become entangled with cultural family beliefs and expectations.

The novel portrays the family, where every relationship, every desire, and every old story is intricately connected. “Sameer threw the ginger at me. Theoretically, a mass

cloning across fated to bring about disaster is rubbish” (Shamsie, 2000, p.122). This playful argument shows how siblings/cousins interact in ways that mix affection and annoyance. The ginger being thrown becomes symbolic of familiarity they can fight, laugh, and challenge each other because of family closeness. Even discussions become emotional and exaggerated. This shows messiness and intimacy in family connections with the playful narration with philosophical skepticism. The speaker presents an extreme theoretical idea, emphasizing that not every hypothetical scenario must end in disaster. The family history is passed down through stories, half-truths, and silences. This leads to misunderstandings, emotional distance, and confusion about identity. Characters like Aliya feel the weight of the family legacy, struggling between respecting tradition and finding her own individuality. “When I tasted that food, I saw Mariam in a kitchen brushing saffron off her husband’s neck and dusting it on to her own lips” (Shamsie, 2000, p.241). Food triggers memory and imagination, showing how family history lives through traditions. The narrator “sees” Mariam in an imagined scene, this shows how family identity and stories are passed down sensually and emotionally, not just through spoken words. The past merges with the present, showing entanglement across generations.

The generations avoid discussing Partition directly, but the silence itself becomes a form of inheritance. The Dard-e-Dil family loses not only land and status, but also a sense of belonging, which later generations like Aliya inherit as an identity crisis. “I thought time was all it took to move on. But how could I be a part of my family and believe that? We are all the walking wounded.” (Shamsie, 2000, p.33). This shows that the family shares emotional wounds that persist across generations. Time alone cannot heal because the trauma is collective. One chooses to cling to the past, while another chooses to escape it. The image of crumbling decay symbolizes the emotional ruins of the family history. The conflict shows that identity can either be defined by grief or rebuilt beyond it, but either way, the past remains powerful. The struggle is not just emotional- it is a struggle for self-definition. The novel shows that identity in the Dard-e-dil family is not simple or individual; it is inherited, questioned, and emotionally charged. The novel portrays the post-independence environment as chaotic because of identity Conflicts. People struggle to define who they are- Pakistani, South Asian, ex-royalty, modern, or traditional. “I can think of no one who knows me who would believe any of that. Maybe not even me. But Aliya, Samia said, A squirrel?”(Shamsie, 2000, p.18). Aliya questions whether her sense of self is real or simply what others have made her believe. The nickname 'squirrel' reflects how identity is shaped by other people’s perception. The novel shows that self-understanding is complicated because memories and labels can distort who we think we are. Truth becomes subjective. The aristocratic families like the Dard-e-dils lose privilege, creating tension between past pride and present reality.

Truth is not only complicated within families, but also in everyday interactions where people pretend and perform. The novel portrays the post-independence environment as chaotic because of identity Conflicts. “Movement across borders breaks old communities and relationships, leading to emotional fragmentation. “But you are the government!... in all your talk. You never mentioned education.” (Shamsie, 2000, p.150). Here, the novel challenges political narratives, exposing how those in power manipulate truth for self-interest. The criticism highlights how truth is shaped by those who control the story whether in politics or family history. The absence of education symbolizes the deliberate withholding of truth from society.

The narrative emphasizes that truth is emotional, selective, and influenced by perspective. “How much salt had been left out in all the stories I'd ever heard... How much salt did I leave out? I left out my own reactions” (Shamsie, 2000, p.179). ‘Salt’ symbolizes emotion, honesty, and personal truth. Aliya realizes that storytelling always involves omission whether to protect ourselves, protect others, or avoid pain. This reveals that memory is selective, and every narrative is incomplete. By leaving out her own reactions, she recognizes the gap between experience and storytelling. The novel shows that truth is not a fixed reality; it is shaped by memory, emotion, perspective, and power. Characters construct stories to cope, to protect themselves, or to maintain family honor.

The novel explores migration, displacement, hybridity, and identity in the context of the Pakistani colonial past. The characters, Aliya and her grandmother Dadi, represent different generations coping with the legacies of colonialism and social hierarchy. A number of studies apply Transgenerational theory or memory studies to the novel. Researchers explore how family secrets and past traumas are passed down through generations. Aliya's attempt to understand her family's mysterious not-quite-twins story shows how the past influences the present. This kind of research focuses on memory and psychological connection across generations. It discusses women's roles in traditional Pakistani families, their freedom, identity, and voice. Aliya's independence and Dadi's traditional authority are often in conflict. Class and social study how Shamsie portrays class divisions within Pakistani society. The upper-class arrogance and the idea of pure lineage are shown through the family's obsession with not-quite-twins. The research focuses on the symbolism of food, language, and memory.

Salt and Saffron symbolize taste, identity, belonging, and cultural heritage. These symbols show how the characters connect emotionally to their past through traditions, stories, and food. Another area of study looks at the diasporic experience, how characters who live abroad, like Aliya, negotiate dual identities between East and West. Transgenerational theory explains how beliefs, behaviors, memories, and even traumas are passed from one generation to another, often unconsciously. The past experiences of our ancestors affect the present generation's identity, emotions, and relationships. Throughout

the story, Aliya's present life is deeply connected to her family's history of not-quite-twins and mysterious events, which creates a sense of inherited mystery and confusion. The Dadi grandmother represents the old generations; she carries memories and values of the aristocratic family. The way she reacts to issues of class, love, and identity reflects the influence of her ancestors' experiences. The family repeats certain behaviors like class prejudice and secrecy. Aliya's journey is about breaking this cycle and finding her own identity, separate from family myths. The stories told by Dadi and other relatives act as a bridge between the past and present.

5. Conclusion

Class differences create divisions in relationships. The India and Pakistan partition serves as a backdrop, with its legacy of separation and resentment in the family's internal conflicts, and the larger socio-cultural context. The *Salt and Saffron* explores identity, class, family relationships, and love that have a great impact on the Indian-Pakistan partition. *Salt and Saffron* explore how family history, identity, memory, and silence shape the lives of individuals in a well-known aristocratic family, which shaped her family's identity across generations. The study aims to examine how *Salt and Saffron* portray the entangled family dynamics of the Dard-e-dil family, where relationships are inherited by stories, silences, and the pressure of maintaining family prestige. The trauma of partition continues to affect generations, through direct memory but through emotional patterns, displacement, and identity

References

- Caruth, C. (2014). *Lost in transmission: Studies of trauma across generations*.
- Khan, U., Uzair, M., & Zeb, S. (2020). Construction of Cultural Identity through Language: A Study of 'Salt and Saffron'. *Global Language Review*, 5(2), 151-159.
- Nazeer, S., Sharif, M. M., Ali, S., & Ahmad, K. (2022). An Analysis of Language Appropriation Techniques used in Kamila Shamsie's *Salt and Saffron*. *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 14(7).
- Riaz, H., & Babae, R. (2015). Inner Alienation: Diasporic Consciousness in Kamila Shamsie's "Salt and Saffron". *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*, 6(5), 163-166.
- Sana, S., & Muhammad, N. (2021). Representation of Pakistani Culture through Code-Mixing: A Critical Analysis of the Novel Holy Woman by Qaisra Shahrzad. *Lingua Cultura*, 15(2), 263-271.
- Shamsie, K. (2011). *Salt and saffron*. A&C Black.
- Shirazi, Q. (2014). Tradition and Modernity in Kamila Shamsie's *Salt and Saffron* (2000). *International Journal of Language, Literature and Culture*, 1(2), 23-27.

Shoaib, M. (2019). Revisiting Indo-Pak History, Gender and Power Relations through Food Tropes in Kamila Shamsie's Novel *Salt and Saffron*. *Journal of Indian Studies*, 5(01), 111-123.